

Reassessing the Economic Burden of Antimicrobial Resistance in Upper- and Lower-Middle-Income Countries: A review on invisible health system and societal cost drivers

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ABSTRACT:

Economic evaluations of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) have predominantly focused on direct medical costs such as drug expenditure, hospitalization, and intensive care utilisation. However, emerging evidence suggests that these approaches substantially underestimate the true economic burden of AMR, particularly in low- and upper- middle income countries, where health system constraints and societal vulnerabilities amplify downstream impacts. This review aimed to map and synthesized the existing evidence on the economic burden of AMR in clinical settings documented in LMICs and UMICs and to develop a conceptual framework that elucidates “invisible” economic drivers amplifying this burden beyond direct healthcare expenditure. This framework illustrates how these mechanisms operate across income settings to inform health technology assessment (HTA) and policy making. Incorporating invisible economic cost domains into HTA, budgeting and AMR policy framework is essential for accurate resource allocation and priority settings.

Keywords: AMR, Economic burden, LMICs and UMICs

Introduction:

Antimicrobial resistance represents substantial clinical and economic consequences, and its need has increased in the twenty-first century due to rising healthcare demands and a global rise in infectious diseases. Every time antibiotics are misused for small illnesses, an entire course is skipped, or the medication is used without a correct diagnosis, we are endangering our future and increasing the financial load that we will eventually be unable to bear.^[1] Antibiotic use is determined by several factors, including the pathogen identified, disease status, location and severity of infection, range of activity, cost, and resistance potential. This makes resistant organisms more expensive to cure than sensitive ones, enabling each patient to borrow money for treatment.

Antibiotic consumption has increased both before and after the COVID-19 pandemic in three different resource contexts. Multi-drug prevalence is lowest in high-income nations, with extremely low antibiotic usage (60.1%) and MDR (29.1%); the Middle East and North Africa have the greatest MDR organism (63.9%), while South Asia has the highest antibiotic use (92.7%).^[2] This is strongly related to significant future financial losses, particularly in low-income environments, which reduces the likelihood of recovery because of the expensive effects of AMR. Lower-income countries will largely be affected due to their huge dependence on labour-based income. Existing estimates have primarily focused on direct healthcare costs and productivity losses, whereas emerging evidence suggests that these approaches substantially underestimate the true economic burden. Beyond measurable expenditures, AMR generates a set of invisible economic drivers like care complexity associated with prolonged hospital stays and ICU stays, health system constraints, workforce strain, opportunity costs, delayed admissions and productivity loss, that distort resource allocation across health systems.^[3] It supports addressing HTA and policy by illustrating the implications of these hidden costs for resource allocation and investment decisions.

INVISIBLE ECONOMIC BURDEN OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE:

The previous exploration of the burden of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) focused solely on direct medical expenses and lost productivity, ICU utilization, increased hospital stays and supportive procedures, which consistently underestimates the actual extent of the damage. The direct cost frameworks give a necessary but imperfect portrayal of AMR impacts, as they do not account for downstream system and societal consequences. However, recent and emerging findings from health economics and system research indicate various invisible economic drivers in AMR, including care complexity, capacity limitations, labour externalities, opportunity costs, and societal output losses. These are created by interconnected elements that are especially common in upper- and lower-middle-income countries, where there is limited space for improvement in the health-care system, and

reallocating resources has direct consequences. The approach will explain why AMR may be an economic distortion at the system level.

Care complexity

Care complexity represents a fundamental mechanism that is under recognized, where antimicrobial resistance increases healthcare costs beyond direct treatment expenditure. AMR increases the clinical uncertainty of the patient, requiring invasive supportive care, broad-spectrum escalation, and frequent diagnostics to compensate for delayed therapeutic effectiveness. Consequently, these expenses are fragmented among several cost centres (laboratory, ICU, pharmacy, imaging study reports, etc.) and therefore not captured as a single attributable cost. So, in resistant infections, delayed pathogen identification and reduced antimicrobial effectiveness generate diagnostic and therapeutic uncertainty. On establishing the association between Antibiotic resistance in intensive care and excess length of stay, there is a substantial increase in excess LOS and resource utilisation of about 15% in three European countries. ^[4]

The AMR does not merely add cost, but it prolongs and intensifies treatment, turning it into resource-intensive episodes. Hospital admissions result in more recurrent diagnostic tests in ICUs and higher lab costs because of repeated cultures for resistant diseases in tertiary hospitals.^[5] Repeated hospitalizations due to treatment failure with previous antibiotics or other comorbidities necessitate antibiotic use, increasing the treatment duration, repetitive investigation and accelerates escalation to second or third line therapies. Also, in intensive care settings, resistant infections frequently require prolonged ventilation support, frequent readmissions, invasive monitoring and multidisciplinary input and thus increasing per patient resource intensity.^[6] In case of nosocomial infections or Gram-negative organisms, the treatment becomes more expensive than non-nosocomial infections.^{[7][8]} This huge out-of-pocket expenditure in LMICs leads to catastrophic health spending, whereas in UMICs, co-payments and uncovered services continue to strain households.

A 1% reduction in inappropriate empirical antimicrobial therapy (IAET) led to a 0.9% reduction in total AMR expenditures, demonstrating how clinical decision inefficiencies exacerbate the economic burden.^[9] Studies were also conducted on Outpatient parenteral antibiotic therapy to shorten the length of hospitalisation. Of the 233 adult patients who received outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy for non-UTI infections, 61% were readmitted due to treatment failure.^[10] Evidence indicates that multidrug infections frequently result in recurrent healthcare utilization with over 60 % of patients experiencing readmissions within one year.

Prolonged hospitalization and escalation to intensive care are prominent signs of AMR-driven care complexity; cost reductions ranged from moderate (Brazil) to substantial levels (Peru). This variation suggests that the invisible costs differ across LMICs and UMICs.^[11] People with low incomes are reported to have higher healthcare expenditures than the educated and high-socioeconomic groups.^[12] Poor quality of life, higher morbidity and

mortality rates are more pronounced effects. Recognizing care complexity as a context-specific economic mechanism rather than a sole clinical consequence is essential for accurately estimating AMR-related costs and establishing policy prioritization in resource limited settings.

Health system constraints

Health system constraints, unlike care complexity, are discussed and operate at the institutional level by eroding healthcare capacity, reducing operational flexibility, and impairing system throughput. As the resistant infection increases, they demand for high intensity resources, particularly sufficient inpatient beds, IUs and isolation facilities. While Tertiary hospitals in low- and middle-income nations have inadequate funding and clinical facilities. AMR increases occupancy in high-dependence units, lowering the capacity for new admissions and increasing readmissions.^[13]

CAP accounted for 43.5% of the 582 readmitted patients with community-acquired pneumonia, while MDR bacteria accounted for 43.2% of the identified pathogens.^[14] Out of 2196 patients, 432 with Gram-negative bacteraemia and a mean age of 70 (\pm 16 years) were readmitted within 30 days due to inadequate empirical antibiotic treatment.^[15] Readmissions occur when a patient returns within 30 days of admission for reasons such as inadequate discharge planning, declining physical health, infection recurrence, poor recovery, or failure of prior treatment. Patients with infectious diseases associated with multidrug resistance account for a certain percentage of readmissions. The cost associated with ventilation support, additional cleaning staff and surveillance system are typically absorbed under hospital overheads and not captured as AMR-specific economic impact.

A decade of cost-effectiveness analysis demonstrates a reduction in index admissions ICU costs with increased LYs and QALYs, underscoring the need to maintain hospital investments in infection control programs.^[16] HAI are more prevalent in LMIC due to a lack of infrastructure, inadequate surveillance, fewer educated physicians and nurses, less funding in healthcare, unstructured policies, poverty, etc.^[17] As a result, low- and middle-income countries bear a disproportionately high burden of infection treatment costs.

There are significant gaps in the implementation of IPC facilities and essential elements to improve low and low-middle-income countries. LMICs want increased assistance for more sustainable and successful IPC programs, antimicrobial stewardship and low-cost, efficient diagnostic tools to lower the dangers, protect patient and healthcare workers' safety. While in UMICs, innovative technologies for diagnosis, therapeutics integrated into most health systems, and data management improve clinical efficiency, they also increase opportunity costs by increasing the load of AMR care within high-intensity, resource-dependent hospital pathways.^[18] Every prolonged stay caused by AMR, particularly in LMIC and UMIC settings, eliminates a significant number of potential admissions, resulting in missed treatment, delayed surgeries, and system inefficiency.

Workforce burden

As disease outbreaks occur, along with demand for medicines, the demand for staff also increases. Many middle and low-income countries lack adequate, qualified staff to treat patients. According to the WHO report of 2025, approximately 78% of the world's nurses are concentrated in countries representing 49% of the global population. So, nurses in low and middle-income countries report burnout and increased overtime, as they face challenges in getting educated and employment.^[19] This may interfere with clinical performance, medication errors, and diagnostic delays by physicians and nurses. On estimating the attributable cost of physician burnout in the U.S at an organizational level, the annual economic cost associated with burnout related to turnover and reduced clinical hours is considerably high.^[20] However, in UMIC contexts, the workforce load manifests predominantly as opportunity costs. Complex AMR cases increase time per patient, documentation requirements, antimicrobial stewardship activities, and coordination among multidisciplinary teams. This can lead to delayed service delivery, particularly in high-volume tertiary hospitals. In LMICs, the burden is seen as service disruption and care quality deterioration due to scarcity, whereas in UMICs it manifests as efficiency loss and opportunity cost.

To guarantee a productive workforce, steps must be taken to improve equitable health outcomes across all socioeconomic backgrounds, when the nation has a favourable demographic dividend. According to a recent WHO report from 2025, infectious illness epidemics reports, AMR increases their prevalence and hospital load while lowering people's life expectancy by 1.8 years.

IPCs must have a stringent implication in low and middle-income countries, where health care delivery and medical hygiene standards are necessary. It makes effective actions at all levels of the health system to achieve quality health care delivery.^[21] But still, stringent actions need to be taken to strengthen IPC Measures, staff training, environmental management to monitor workforce protection and management tools. 78 hospitals following IPC core components are monitored in Kazakhstan found with an improved training system. This also regulates staff training, avoids staff overload and burnout^[21]. Monitoring mental health, equitable job distribution, promoting gender equity, and workforce well-being are the next target goals of global policymakers for the upcoming years.^[22] Incorporating workforce externalities into health technology assessment and policy planning is therefore critical for properly estimating the economic returns of AMR mitigation strategies.

Opportunity costs

Opportunity costs represent health and economic gains that are foregone rather than expenditures that are incurred. In the context of AMR, opportunity costs arise when scarce health system, household and societal resources are diverted toward managing resistant

infections, thereby displacing investments in prevention, primary care and economic productivity. Due to LMICs' inadequate baseline service capacity, every extended AMR-related admission has a significant marginal opportunity cost, resulting in overcrowding out of essential services like immunization and basic infectious disease control. At the household level, lost wages affect household survival, forcing trade-offs between healthcare spending and essential needs such as nutrition and education.

It is primarily caused by an absolute lack of healthcare capacity at LMIC tertiary hospitals. In contrast, in UMICs, the opportunity cost of AMR is largely about efficiency loss in high-volume hospital systems. From a health economic perspective, opportunity costs imply a misallocation of scarce resources caused by AMR-related inefficiencies rather than clinical prioritization.^[23] AMR evaluations include drug costs, LOS and hospital charges but fail to account for factors like beds unavailable, services of other patients and delayed emergency care.

Societal productivity loss

Societal productivity loss constitutes a critical component of the economic burden of antimicrobial resistance that extends beyond healthcare system into households, labour market and the broader economy.

AMR in LMICs affects households operating within informal labour markets. Prolonged illness, repeated hospital visits, and caregiving demand directly translate into income loss with any social protection mechanisms. So, in case of recurrent infections and treatment failures, especially in LMICs, it affects patients and caregivers, pushing them into financial distress. While estimating the expenses at the national level, the societal impact of the ABR indicates that the attributable cost of productivity loss is higher for premature death than direct healthcare costs. 90% of the overall cost associated with premature death relies on the severity and type of infection.^[22] These are not highlighted in hospital-based cost estimates and are poorly addressed in studies. AMR generates substantial long-term and irreversible opportunity costs through loss of labour output, reinforcing the need for a societal perspective on economic frameworks.^[24]

According to World Bank group projections, low-income nations' yearly GDP would begin to decline by 2050 because of antibiotics becoming ineffective against resistant infections worldwide, plunging them into severe financial difficulties. Also, AMR imposes a measurable macroeconomic burden in UMICs, with national-level cost estimates approaching a significant proportion of GDP.^[9] Among the extra costs spent by the patient, 30% resulted from productivity loss by presenteeism and absenteeism from work.^[25] Also, the proportion of individuals signed up for a health insurance policy is far lower, and very few are from a lower socioeconomic background, resulting in out-of-pocket expenditure.^[26]

S.NO	STUDY (YEAR)	STUDY TYPE	PATHOGENS	STUDY COUNTRY	KEY OUTCOMES
1	Incremental cost of AMR infections among hospitalised patients (2024) ^[27]	Prospective study	<i>Enterobacteriaceae</i> , <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> , <i>Staphylococcus</i>	Multicenter hospitals, India	Increased LOS, ↑direct and indirect hospital cost, and productivity loss
2	Excess resource use and the cost of drug-resistant infections (2024) ^[28]	Bayesian meta – analysis and Systematic review	Six priority AMR pathogens	European hospitals	↑bed days, ↑ICU cost, excess per case cost, excess primary care cost, excess outpatient cost
3	Burden of nosocomial infections in ICU patients (2024) ^[29]	Cross- sectional study	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , and Enterococcus spp.	ICU hospitals, Iran	ICU stay ↑ from approx. 5- 30 days
4	Health and economic burden of AMR in Australian hospitals (2019) ^[30]	Population-based model	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , <i>Enterococcus faecium</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	National hospital model, Australia	Opportunity cost and block bed capacity
5	Excess burden of antibiotic-resistant bloodstream infections (2024) ^[31]	Retrospective cohort	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> , <i>Enterobacteriaceae</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , Enterococcus species, and <i>Pseudomon</i>	Multicenter hospitals, Chile	Excess LOS, excess cost, DALYs and productivity loss

			<i>as aeruginosa</i>		
6	Direct economic cost of AMR bloodstream infections in neonates (2025) [32]	Cross-sectional study, Micro-costing	MDR Gram-negative bacteria	Perinatal ICU, Peru	↑ ICU stay, ↑ diagnostic and treatment cost and increase in LOS
7	Mortality, LOS and healthcare costs of MDR infections in the elderly (2022) [33]	Retrospective cohort	MDR bacteria	Hospitals USA	High attributable LOS, Mortality, Inpatient cost
8	Carbapenem-resistant <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> infections (2024) [34]	Retrospective observational study	Carbapenem-resistant <i>A. baumannii</i>	Tertiary hospital	ICU dependence, prolonged ventilation, care complexity
9	Economic cost of CRE healthcare-associated infections (2022) [35]	Costing cohort study	CRE	Acute care hospital singapore	↑ direct cost, ↑ lost bed-days (opportunity cost)
10	MDR <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> hospital burden (2023) [36]	Retrospective case-control study	MDR <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Hospital series	Prolonged Hospitalisation, ICU escalation
11	CR <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> bloodstream infections	Retrospective cohort study	Carbapenem resistant <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Multicentred hospitals, China	↑ ICU admission, ↑ LOS, Mortality

	(2023) ^[37]				
12	Community-acquired ABR urinary tract infections (2024) ^[38]	Systematic review, Meta-analysis	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>Klebsiella</i>	Hospitalized UTI patients	↑ Hospital LOS, ↑ treatment and rare cost
13	Length of stay and cost of resistant <i>Salmonella</i> infections (2025) ^[39]	Systematic review and Meta-analysis	Resistant <i>Salmonella spp.</i>	Multi-country data	Longer LOS higher treatment costs.
14	Attributable LOS and cost of healthcare-associated infections (2021) ^[40]	Retrospective cohort study	Multiple resistant pathogens	Multi-site hospitals	Attributable LOS and hospital cost estimates
15	Bloodstream infections and AMR in ICUs during the COVID-19 era (2024) ^[41]	Observational ICU stays	MDR bacteria and fungi	ICU hospitals	ICU congestion increased diagnostics and antimicrobial escalation
16	Economic burden of Carbapenam resistant <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (2025) ^[42]	Hospital linked economic analysis	Carbapenam resistant <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Hospitals, China	↑per case cost, DALYs, productivity loss
17	Socioeconomic burden of ABR in Fragile settings (2021) ^[43]	Systematic scoping review	MDR <i>Acinetobacter</i> CRE	Refugee hospitals	Extreme LOS, ICU pressure system inefficiency
18	ICU outcomes of	Multi-center retrospective	Carbapenem-resistant	ICU hospital	Very prolonged

	CR – <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (2025) [44]	observational study	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (CRAB)		ICU stay
19	MRSA infection vs colonization cost analysis (2024) [45]	Retrospective study	MRSA	Tertiary hospitals Singapore	Excess LOS, excess health care cost
20	Readmission in community Acquired Pneumonia (2022) [14]	Retrospective cross-sectional study	MDR	tertiary hospital Vietnam	Increase in readmissions.

Table [1]: Evidence highlighting the key outcomes observed in studies carried out in different income settings

Figure 1: Invisible economic drivers of AMR

The table [1] demonstrates a systematic pattern of resource intensification driven by specific resistant pathogens and care settings. Across LMICs and UMICs, carbapenem-resistant Gram-negative organisms- particularly *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* – are consistently associated with disproportionate ICU utilisation, prolonged length of stay, and recurrent admissions. This supports the policy makers on pathogen prioritised HTA, bundles payments and infection control investments.

Because most of the information is gathered from tertiary sector institutions, the data indicate a consistent set of pathogens that are resistant to high-end restricted antibiotics, reducing treatment options and increasing morbidity and mortality. This underestimation is more pronounced in lower and upper-middle-income countries, where a limited health system leads to downstream economic effects of resistant infections.^{[46][47]}

Although *Table [1]* primarily reports hospital-based outcomes like length of stay, ICU utilisation, readmissions and excess costs and its relevant to the outcomes that indirectly represent the invisible economic burden. It provides empirical evidence of care pathways and system disruptions. The comparative framework presented in the table says about the hospital-level burden of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens aligned with HTA principles rather than pathogen prioritisation alone. Importantly, this also includes multidrug-resistant bloodstream infections, which highlight how infection severity and site of infection can amplify resource use irrespective of the pathogen involved.

A recent systematic review was published; it addressed the limitations that were encountered in the studies. Where the studies failed to address one or multiple points like direct cost, indirect costs, productivity loss, cost of treatment related to ADR with Antibiotics, cost of welfare services, and additional costs associated with human and health resources of implementing approaches or future health costs.^[48] Few studies failed to address various invisible economic factors that drives AMR costs.

Thus, AMR-related economic burden emerges from the interaction between pathogen resistance, host vulnerability and institutional care practices, rather than from resistance status in isolation. These findings directly align with HTA principles by demonstrating how AMR distorts allocative efficiency and system throughput, highlighting pathogen – prioritised infection control, stewardship investments and bundled payment reforms.

DOMAIN	LMIC	UMIC
Care complexity	Diagnostic delays	Escalation intensity
Workforce burden	Scarcity	Efficiency loss

Opportunity cost	Absolute bed loss	Throughput loss
Societal loss	Informal income shock	Absenteeism

Table [2] *Operation of invisible AMR costs differ across income settings*

These cross- income differences indicate that a single costing framework cannot be applied uniformly across settings, reinforcing the need for HTA models that explicitly incorporate income specific invisible cost mechanisms.

POLICY AND HTA IMPLEMENTATION:

Health technology assessment and evidence-based policy implementation have become critical in strengthening the global health system, as governments face an increasing economic burden from antimicrobial resistance and the development of new antibiotics. For researchers, LMICs often gives potential data challenges, and the AMR cost burden is not well accounted.^[49] So, in high-, middle-, and low-income nations, the structure of health funding and insurance systems impacts how well HTA evidence is incorporated into benefit package design, pricing, and reimbursement processes.

In middle-income nations such as India, China, and Thailand have made inconsistent advances in using HTA for policy choices. While in low-middle-income countries, it relies heavily on donor funding, community-based insurance and a fragmented public system. Adopting HTA include poor cost data availability, weak digital infrastructure and less research capacity. The BMJ Global Health (2024) report on India's Ayushman Bharat PM-JAY is a significant case study for how HTA is gradually translating into policy reforms in MICs. The study examines how the evolution of PM-JAY benefit packages reflects the move from expert opinion-driven decision making to structured cost data, stakeholder consultations, costing studies, and preliminary HTA inputs.^[50] The study also identifies ongoing obstacles, such as a lack of studies for diagnostics, surgical procedures, and infection-related hospital care, as well as insufficient staff capability to analyse HTA data. The gap reflects greater constraints faced by MIC and LIC countries and highlights a need for developing a systematic cost data system, enhancing hospital reporting, and multidisciplinary HTA expertise.

To implement policy and assure alignment, policymakers should first ensure that national AMR surveillance systems are expanded to incorporate economic and operational indicators such as ICU bed days, which are linked to resistant infections and readmission rates. Second, HTA authorities should create methodological guidelines for including invisible cost domains into economic assessments of AMR solutions. Also, this must involve cross divisional collaboration between other ministries like health and finance to ensure the AMR policies reflect their full economic and societal ramifications.

Using micro costing for immediate, direct medical expenditures and macro costing for broader, long-term indirect costs allows for a more fair, realistic, and methodologically sound

evaluation of AMR's entire economic impact. This provides policymakers with clarity and a better understanding of the problem.^[49]

CONCLUSION:

The review identified evidence indicating that AMR causes a substantial economic burden that extends beyond direct medical costs, operating through various invisible mechanisms like increased care complexity, health system constraints, workforce strain, opportunity costs and societal productivity losses. Evidence from LMICs and UMICs indicates that resistant infections- particularly Gram-negative pathogens- are consistently associated with prolonged hospitalization, ICU dependence, readmissions and blocked bed capacity. The findings underscore the need to move beyond pathogen level cost reporting toward integrated economic frameworks that capture both health system and societal consequences of AMR. Incorporating invisible cost domains into health technology assessment, budgeting and policy design is essential. Future research must adopt a mixed costing approach combining direct medical care costs and the cost of indirect and long-term impacts to provide more accurate estimates on the economic burden of antimicrobial resistance

Abbreviations:

1. ABR -Antibiotic Resistance
2. AMR – Antimicrobial Resistance
3. Approx - Approximately
4. BMJ – British Medical Journal
5. BSI- Blood stream infection
6. CAP – Community Acquired Pneumonia
7. CRAB- Carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii*
8. CRE -Carbapenem Resistant Enterobacterial
9. CRKP – Carbapenem Resistant *Klebsiella pneumonia*
10. CRPA – Carbapenem Resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*
11. DALYs – Disability Adjusted Life Year
12. E. Coli – Escherichia Coli
13. ESBL – Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase
14. GDP – Gross Domestic Product
15. HAI – Healthcare Associated Infection/Hospital acquired infection
16. HTA – Health Technology Assessment
17. ICU – Intensive care unit
18. IEAT- Inappropriate empirical antibiotic therapy
19. IPC – Infection Prevention and Control
20. LMIC – Low Middle-Income Countries
21. LOS – Length of Stay
22. MDR - Multi Drug Resistance
23. MDRO - Multi Drug Resistant Organism
24. MIC – Middle Income Countries
25. MRSA – Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

26. MSSA – Methicillin Susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus*
27. NICE – National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
28. PBS – Positive Behavior Support
29. PM-JAY – Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana
30. QALYs – Quality Adjusted Life Years
31. UTI – Urinary Tract Infection
32. WHO – World Health Organization
33. XDRO – Extensively Drug-Resistant Organism

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